
Can buzzwords create infrastructures? Reflecting on the Water-Energy-Food Nexus approach

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Abstract

Over the past few decades, the increasing pressures on water, energy and food have widened social inequalities and furthered environmental damage. The scholarship on the Water-Energy-Food Nexus (WEF Nexus) has responded with policy-oriented interdisciplinary research on modelling the use of environmental resources. While the WEF Nexus covers some elements of complexity, it has been critiqued by social scientists for ignoring questions of power and justice. On the other hand, the WEF Nexus has succeeded in mobilising funding and the attention of policymakers. How have sustainability researchers used the 'WEF Nexus' buzzword to engage with complexity and what are the underlying capabilities required to support this engagement?

While current reviews of the WEF Nexus research focus on methodologies for integration and optimisation, we examine nexus research as an interdisciplinary practice, contingent on capabilities and politics. As such, we show how the WEF Nexus programme engaged with the notion of complexity, while acknowledging the notions of power and justice. We argue that the WEF Nexus buzzword was successful in building cognitive capabilities for researching complexity by giving researchers the flexibility to reconceptualise it as well as the freedom to assemble novel configurations of teams. However, the time-limited nature of the hype around the Nexus meant that researchers and programme leads were less able to translate their research agendas into transgressive, political action. This was particularly visible in the case of early career and overseas scholars who did not have the pre-existing 'backstage' capabilities, i.e. networks, access to relevant software or domain-specific knowledge.

Keywords: water-energy-food nexus; sustainability; buzzword; capability approach; knowledge infrastructure; complexity

1. Introduction

In August 2016, several hundred human geographers gathered in London for the major annual conference in their field (Royal Geographical Society, 2016). The theme of the event was 'nexus thinking', a phrase directly referencing one of the most popular environmental policy framings at the time, namely, 'the water-food-energy Nexus' (WEF Nexus). The WEF Nexus, as conceptualised by the United Nations agencies, promised to develop tools for integrated analysis of benefits and trade-offs across water, energy and food systems (Bazilian *et al.*, 2011). While human geographers have always embraced pluralism and porosity of ideas, borrowing a conference theme from the world of policy and environmental management was an unusual move. Have academics succumbed to the recent policy fad? Or are they trying to take advantage of the popularity – and perhaps ambiguity – of the WEF Nexus framing?

Prof Andy Stirling, the Co-I of the Nexus Network+ (NN+), gave the keynote speech during the event. The NN+ was a £1.5 million research programme funded by the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) between 2014-2018. Its aim was developing social science-led approaches to tackling complex issues across water, energy and food domains (Cairns, Wilsdon and O'Donovan, 2017). Prof Stirling, with his career spanning across STS, Human Geography and policy advice, offered a thought-provoking angle on the possibilities of operationalising the WEF Nexus by critical social scientists. In his view, academia faced no shortage of theories and methods to conceptualise complexity in sustainability (with references made to ideas as disparate as cost-benefit analysis, Delphi methods, relational ontologies). However, the major shortcoming of the complexity scholarship lied in the practices of interdisciplinary knowledge production and dissemination. Complexity scholarship was—perhaps ironically—being developed in siloes and failed to communicate its value to influence the politics of sustainability in a meaningful way. To Stirling, the promise of the WEF Nexus lied in its power to reach decisionmakers (Stirling, 2015 and 2016).

Still, the WEF Nexus has been dismissed by some social scientists for championing a technocratic outlook on climate issues, ignoring the questions of power and re-inventing already existing conceptualisations (Allouche, Middleton and Gyawali, 2015). According to Cairns and Krzywoszynska¹ (2016), the WEF Nexus is a buzzword: 'a popular term characterised with strong normative resonance and ambiguity'. Buzzwords appropriate the language to suit particular agendas, indicate desirable futures and influence the doable scope of actions (*ibid.*). At best, the WEF Nexus is a meaningless term, at worst, a reactionary one. An interesting tension emerges here – can a progressive research agenda be developed using a contentious policy framing?

It is worth noting that Stirling did not solely present from an academic standpoint. The proposed argument also spoke to his role as the lead of a major research programme. NN+ was an investment explicitly granted to build capabilities for social science research on sustainability, to link scholars to practitioners and to co-design engaged research connecting water, energy and food domains (UKRI, 2018). In that reading, the legacy of the WEF Nexus rhetoric is less important than what the NN+-funded researchers do as a part of the programme. In effect, this allows an investigation of

situated practices rather than discourses of researchers, funders and programme managers.

In this article, we will reflect on the WEF Nexus as a fad that reached its peak in mid-2010s. Based on a case study of the Nexus Network+ programme and its researchers, we aim to examine the relationship between the hype surrounding the WEF Nexus and its power to build capabilities for inter- and transdisciplinary sustainability research on complex issues. Our paper addresses the following questions: How did sustainability researchers utilise the 'WEF Nexus' buzzword to engage with complexity and what are the underlying human capabilities required to support this engagement? More broadly, how do fashionable concepts like the WEF Nexus shape scientific fields? We argue that the WEF Nexus buzzword was successful in building the cognitive capabilities for researching complexity by allowing researchers flexibility to reconceptualise it as well as the freedom to assemble novel configurations of teams. However, the time-limited nature of the hype around the WEF Nexus meant that researchers and programme leads were less able to translate their research agendas into transgressive, political action. This was particularly visible in the case of early career scholars who did not have the pre-existing 'backstage' capabilities, i.e. networks, access to relevant software or domain-specific knowledge.

This paper's primary theoretical contribution is to bring together STS literature on the promissory discourses around science with the recent advancements in the field of knowledge infrastructure studies. While knowledge infrastructure studies have been historically concerned with IT and engineering resources supporting knowledge production (e.g. laboratories, datasets; Karasti et al., 2016), there has been a recent recognition of the more intangible ways research is enabled (Edwards, 2020; Aicardi and Mahfoud, 2024). Within that, we posit that the concepts of 'capabilities for research' (O'Donovan et al. 2022) and 'buzzwords' (Bensaude-Vincent, 2014) can be productively operationalised vis-a-vis knowledge infrastructure studies. Our target audience are STS researchers from the above fields, sustainability researchers and funding bodies.

The remainder of the article will proceed as follows. Section 2 will introduce our analytical framework: a summary of STS studies concerning buzzwords and hype in research as well as a brief overview of the idea of capabilities in the context of knowledge infrastructures. Section 2 will also provide background to the origin of the WEF Nexus, together with main criticisms and expectations for the future of this research agenda. Section 3 will summarise our research methodology. Section 4 will discuss the results. In the section 5, we conclude the article, pointing to the ongoing relevance of buzzwords in science beyond the WEF Nexus framing. Even though the popularity of the WEF Nexus has faded, the research culture is brimming with buzzwords. Whether the next major funding agenda will concern Artificial Intelligence, Net Zero or Digital Twins, it is important to reflect on the opportunities and constraints those buzzwords carry.

2. Analytical perspectives

2.1. Water-Energy-Food Nexus as knowledge infrastructure

Over the past few decades, sustainability researchers and practitioners have recognised the need for developing methods and theories which address the complexity of the relationships between humans and nature. Concepts like 'system boundaries', 'planetary limits', and 'emergence' have been operationalised to focus on the spaces in-between the traditional domains of expertise (Rockström et al. 2009; Kallis, 2019). Likewise, the methodological advances in soft systems, integrated greenhouse gas emissions accounting or Agent-Based Modelling have been promoted in policy evaluation spaces as tools capable of embracing plural perspectives or reducing complex problems to effective decision-making strategies (Barbrook-Johnson et al. 2021).

In the early 2010s, the Water-Energy-Food Nexus (WEF Nexus) joined this growing toolbox for addressing complexity. According to proponents, WEF Nexus frameworks combine the interdisciplinary expertise and produce novel methods of environmental modelling with which to evaluate policy trade-offs and synergies resulting from interventions in and interactions between water, energy and food systems (Bazilian *et al.*, 2011). WEF Nexus approaches have been applied to the numerous high-profile research projects which produced new assessment tools for sustainability (e.g. Magic NEXUS, WEFWEB, Foreseer, WEF Nexus Tool 2.0; (see Michalec, 2020 for a review).

In practice, these WEF Nexus approaches can be characterised as complex *knowledge infrastructures*, sociotechnical systems consisting of various interacting actors, agents and components (Edwards et al. 2013). Some of these elements are technological: software, computers and other artifacts. Some are social: research groups, funders, standards, budgets, institutions and political arrangements. These entities contribute to the processes by which knowledge is created and applied, as well as the devices, networks and institutions which support these activities (Karasti et al 2016). STS scholarship on knowledge infrastructures is useful to us because it helps us account for how groups of scientists and programme managers with different intents and disciplinary traditions attempt to build useful resources together. Unlike taking a starting point in social structure, which can be over-determined, thinking infrastructurally allows the possibility that knowledge infrastructures might be otherwise. Actors, according to Cardwell et al. (2024) don't just work within the contexts of knowledge infrastructures, they work on those contexts.

2.2. Critiques of the WEF Nexus

The main criticism leveraged against those early WEF Nexus approaches was that they did not address the need for a deeper systemic change, effectively disengaging with the political complexity of climate change (Williams, Bouzarovski and Swyngedouw, 2014; Cairns and Krzywoszynska, 2016). Scholars offer a variety of suggestions in terms of what counts as 'systemic change': some define it as a departure from the reliance on fossil fuels (Stephens, 2014), while others argue for transition to a postgrowth economy (Allouche, Middleton and Gyawali, 2015). Meanwhile, the WEF Nexus approaches remained epistemically committed to the environmental

management methods they emerged from. The framing of policy trade-offs went often unquestioned, while the synergies between various environmental domains didn't account of other externalities (e.g. desalination plant projects for supporting agriculture in arid regions not considering the very existence of energy and water requirements or their complex transboundary geopolitics; Williams, Bouzarovski and Swyngedouw, 2014; Allouche, Middleton and Gyawali, 2015).

These critiques point to how emerging WEF Nexus framings infrastructurally concealed complex power dynamics of environmental policymaking. As shown by Cardwell et al. (2024), as ways of knowing become infrastructurally powerful, those infrastructures in turn marginalise alternatives. Indeed, infrastructures shape ways of knowing precisely because it is easiest to know by using existing infrastructures. Going against the grain, in this case by innovating epistemically narrow methods, is difficult and risks marginalising scholars already active in the field (ibid). We see evidence of this charge in the way in which many of the tools from WEF Nexus literature aim to provide 'optimal' solutions by accounting for the combined resource use under certain scenarios (Daher and Mohtar, 2015). In reality, the chances of obtaining an optimal policy solution are limited by the study boundaries (i.e. it's impossible to take all relevant considerations into account), the availability of good quality local data and acknowledging the so-called bounded rationality of decision makers (Gottbauer and Van den Bergh, 2011). Sanitised models, upon entering the real world, fail to reconcile with decision-makers' biases, power struggles and the inherent uncertainties of sustainability expertise (Stirling, 2015).

Finally, and related to prior epistemic commitments to optimisation logics, WEF Nexus scholarship was criticised for its narrow applicability, for instance, usually excluding social science perspectives – a systematic review by Albrecht, Crotoft and Scott (2018) which analysed 245 WEF Nexus-type outputs, revealed that the literature strongly favoured quantitative approaches (nearly three quarters of the papers reviewed), while only one quarter of the research crossed disciplinary boundaries and approximately one in five applied mixed methods.

2.3. Buzzwords as linguistic technology

By 2016, these critiques were well-rehearsed in the literature and were a feature of debate at that year's annual Royal Geographic Society conference in London as we have discussed. This was a remarkable situation, WEF Nexus framings were at once an organising device for the United Kingdom's biggest geography event of the year, as well as a focus of much intellectual debate. What was this nexus buzz all about, and what, if anything, was it doing to existing knowledge infrastructures? To answer that question, we need to understand how exactly buzzwords influence science.

Many past attempts to conceptualise environmental complexity, such as 'sustainable development' (Luke, 2005; Brown, 2015) and 'smart city' (Michalec et al., 2019; Shelton et al., 2015), have often been seen as buzzwords. These buzzwords play various roles in constructing scientific knowledge. They can act as 'empty signifiers' that fail to inspire future-oriented thinking (Brown, 2015) or as ambiguous terms that do not specify whose needs they address (Luke, 2005). They can also create 'hype

cycles' (Rip, 2014) and facilitate complex discussions (Mollers, 2017). We argue that buzzwords can perform all these roles simultaneously, allowing researchers to either simplify, obscure, or embrace complexities based on the context and needs.

Buzzwords are often criticised for oversimplifying complexity. For example, Halpern et al. (2013) critique test bed infrastructure in smart city projects for masking real-world complexity with simplified assumptions, ultimately undermining democratic processes (Halpern et al., 2013; Nyborg et al., 2023). Similarly, Luke (2005) argues that the buzz around 'sustainable development' reduces complex issues to simple, often ineffective solutions. These critiques suggest that buzzwords can blur conceptual advancements and, at worst, enable powerful actors to maintain the status quo under the guise of social transformation.

However, viewing buzzwords solely as 'empty vessels' that empower incumbents overlooks their potential to propel scientific progress. Arie Rip (2014) highlights how buzzwords, through 'hype' and 'issue attention' cycles, can shape scientific decisions by building attention, defining issues, and attracting investments (Downs, 1972). This convening power influences what research gets funded, published, and valued, thereby shaping scientific priorities.

Buzzwords then are not just empty concepts but 'linguistic technologies' (Bensaude-Vincent, 2014) that build consensus, set agendas, and foster collaborations at and between existing knowledge infrastructure. It is precisely their lack of conceptual clarity that is crucial for shaping scientific research. By indicating desired research directions and funding them, buzzwords enable collaborations among scientists with diverse perspectives. According to Bensaude-Vincent (2014), this ambiguity is constructive because it allows interpretive flexibility while being recognizable enough to adapt to different contexts.

This is especially useful when it comes to interdisciplinary research: buzzwords help avoid conflict by allowing parties to focus on abstract goals rather than specific methods or politics (Mollers, 2017). This so-called 'tailoring' of research objectives enables progress without threatening established boundaries (ibid.). Thus, buzzwords are not merely 'empty signifiers' (Brown, 2015). However, their convening power does not guarantee high-quality research or its translation into policy.

2.4 Infrastructuration of the WEF Nexus and its practices

So how might we understand the influence of these linguistic technologies on knowledge infrastructure? The buzz around the WEF Nexus both contributed to and was enhanced by funder interventions such as the ESRC Nexus Network+ investment. Appraising this situation infrastructurally here is useful for two reasons. First, infrastructure, while obdurate in character, are also mutable. Scientific infrastructures afford ways of knowing but do not completely determine them, hence we should expect to find processes of change and be prepared to analytically unpack them (Cardwell et al., 2024).

Edwards et al. (2019) refer to these processes of shifting knowledge--and crucially agency--as infrastructurationⁱⁱ. This happens when infrastructures become embedded in the habits and skills of individuals:

'all infrastructures require users to learn and adopt these behavioural regularities. Once rendered fully habitual or incorporated into widely diffused organizational routines, such regularities can be regarded as components of infrastructure. They play a key role in the phenomenon of invisibility or transparency in well-functioning infrastructures.' (ibid. 2019 p.358)

Certainly, we can see the outcome of these processes in some of the diverse approaches to questions of complexity and integration have been incorporated into WEF Nexus infrastructures. Publications, including outputs from the NN+ projects, have started to consider the interdependencies between social and ecological systems and deepening of collaborations with practitioners and communities (Cairns, Wilsdon and O'Donovan, 2017; Foden et al., 2019; Hoolohan et al., 2019). For instance, Urbinatti's *et al.*, (2020) paper on 'opening up' expertise in nexus discussions contributed to the developments of methods for science-policy integration. Their analysis points out to the need to incorporate methods which explicitly engage with diverse stakeholders and disciplines, using humility as a guiding principle of interactions.

Here our attention to practices in knowledge infrastructure reveals not just stakes that are epistemic, but also deeply political. For Allouche (2024, p. 503), WEF Nexus frames not merely technical sites of evolving complexity, but locations of 'the interplay of different types of power, as well as the actors wielding them'. Stirling (2024, p. 10) addresses these politics in terms of the 'directionality' of research: 'in senses that go beyond mere driving of established innovation processes, to also include at least some degree of politically-deliberate steering.' Echoing the warning he addressed to the RGS in August 2016, Stirling (2024) adds that 'if taken without reference to a crucial broader context, all such efforts can fall far short of addressing the full plural implications of notions of direction.' Appraising infrastructuration as practices in context then is critical.

The second useful aspect of an infrastructural approach is distinguishing between the formal and informal knowledge apparatus. Aicardi and Mahfoud (2024, p. 405) make an important distinction between more formal 'facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation' (e.g., both orthodox WEF Nexus toolsets and the NN+ programme itself) and informal and often invisible forms of knowledge production and collaboration (e.g. ways researchers facilitate discussions or write together). The implication here is that formal interdisciplinary knowledge infrastructures are often in tension with the actual ways that researchers work, 'often disconnected from people's everyday practices and do not acknowledge already existing forms of cooperation' (Aicardi and Mahfoud, 2024 p. 406). To understand the impact of the WEF Nexus buzz we must carefully assess the infrastructure that the ESRC built, the Nexus Network+ programme, while at the same time also looking at the informal practices that scientists actually perform.

2.5. Understanding capabilities that underpin knowledge infrastructures

The rest of this article builds on the two insights introduced earlier: 1) the infrastructuring of new knowledge through practices and research programmes 2) the positioning of sustainability researchers vis-a-vis WEF Nexus buzzword and the surrounding hype. We do this by mobilising the analysis that appraises the human capabilities necessary to cultivate and fulfil inter- and transdisciplinary practices and, in the long run, knowledge infrastructures. Human capabilities are the freedoms to pursue and achieve activities that people have real reason to value (Sen, 1999). Our analysis follows Sen in seeing the human capabilities valued by researchers as a matter of empirical identification (Sen, 1999). Therefore, by mapping capabilities valued by interdisciplinary researchers themselves, we use human capabilities as a space of evaluation with which to assess subjectivities, institutions and practices based on individual and public values (Robeyns, 2016).

The main advantage of this approach lies in providing an opportunity to create explanations for the cultivation of new practices at an analytic level below that of the knowledge infrastructure. This is important because the practice of any research method will depend on the availability to research team of a particular set of capabilities (Stirling, 2015). Recall, according to Edwards et al. (2019, 358):

'Infrastructuring works by the acquisition and inheritance of necessary habits, skills and social norms, their constant performance and rehearsal – which is, after all, what makes them habits, skills and norms. They not only shape our minds and bodies, but also serve as vital components of infrastructure; they help explain how infrastructures work and why they endure'

Our capabilities framework is consistent with this perspective as it emphasises material, discursive and institutional contingency and situatedness of capabilities (Robeyns, 2005). It also directs us to how researchers might value specific capabilities differently depending on the context of the project and knowledge infrastructure established around it.

Further, another advantage of mapping the capabilities actually valued by researchers is that we bypass concerns with assessing only the intent of infrastructure funders and programme managers, and by doing so assess practices and their underlying capabilities valued by researchers themselves. For instance, our previous research identified three ways of developing capabilities through and for interdisciplinary sustainability research (O'Donovan et al., 2022). First, mobilising '*cognitive capabilities*' by integrating discipline-specific knowledge within teams of multi-disciplinary colleagues. Second, cultivating '*transgressive capabilities*', that is the ability to challenge existing power relations, gatekeeping, and incumbent orthodox practices that prevent the advancement of new (inter)disciplines. Third, the creation and maintenance of what we called '*backstage capabilities*', which included a varied assortment of capabilities such as the nurturing of long-standing professional networks (O'Donovan et al., 2022).

From here, we will use the case of the Nexus Network+ to examine how researchers mobilise buzzwords as 'linguistic technologies' to leverage capabilities for transdisciplinary research. In doing so we demonstrate that, while buzzwords do

indeed allow researchers to leverage their capabilities in novel ways, they require pre-existing capabilities to be in place to leverage the opportunity. Similarly, we tend not to see the creation of novel capabilities through the use of buzzwords, with implications for the increasingly targeted and mission-oriented research funding space.

3. Methodology

The paper analyses data from a large inter- and transdisciplinary research programme, the Nexus Network+ (NN+). In 2014, the NN+ was funded in order to promote building networks and research capabilities at the intersection of water, energy, and food domains (Cairns, Wilsdon and O'Donovan, 2017). The NN+ funded five awards of £60,000-£120,000, for original research projects running between 2016 and 2018. The research projects were diverse in their scope (e.g., water, energy, food consumption at home; agriculture modelling, citizen-led land surveying; food security governance; domestic fuel use), however, each project committed to the social-science led understanding of the WEF Nexus while collaborating with practitioners and researchers across other disciplines.

Our research was motivated by the need to critically engage with the notion of research evaluation. Rather than looking how researchers and practitioners made impact within the timeframes of the project, we enquired what capabilities were needed to mobilise successful projects in the first instance, and, going further, what capabilities WEF Nexus projects generated as a result of the NN+ funding. For that reason, our unit of analysis are both NN+ research projects as well as the research programme as a whole. We gathered the first set of data through an observation of two workshops in June 2015 and May 2018 which gathered researchers from across the NN+ Partnership Grant portfolio (Ayre and O'Donovan, 2018). Participants were invited to reflect on capabilities within their projects by building their own maps of stakeholders, project participants, socio-material relations, resources and institutions (Schiffer, 2007). We complemented workshops with semi-structured interviews, where we spoke to 15 recipients of the NN+ Partnership grants to gauge experiences of research collaborations. We conducted the interviews between July and September 2018; conversations lasted between 40 to 120 minutes. Through our conversations, we sought to elicit participants' narratives of interdisciplinarity, complexity, career progression and the timelines of their respective projects.

Interview transcripts and event memos were coded using qualitative data analysis software. Our approach to integrating the insights from different types of qualitative data was informed by narrative analysis (Herman and Vervaeck, 2019). Open and inductive coding we used allowed focusing on the first person's experiences of engaging with the nexus and capabilities needed to successfully collaborate. For an in-depth discussion of the research design and further details on NN+ projects please refer to (O'Donovan et al., 2022).

Finally, we wanted to reflect on our positionality. All authors were employed by the NN+ programme, with OM and JM present in its final six-months as evaluators while COD employed for two years as research manager. Additionally, OM was a PhD

student on a WEF Nexus programme between 2016-2019, which was helpful for developing familiarity with the literature as well as the associated critique. Being embedded in the NN+ programme allowed us to develop a relationship with the managers and the recipients of the NN+ grants, which resulted in a rich dataset and frequent (albeit informal) points of contact. Thanks to our involvement in the NN+, we were in the middle of the hype rather than on the margins, witnessing first-hand researchers' excitement and struggles during workshops and conferences.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Cognitive capabilities for nexus thinking: towards embracing complexity

Our research shows that the WEF Nexus was successful in mobilising capabilities for researching complexity. However, our findings indicate that this mainly operated through cognitive capabilities allowing researchers to transcend disciplinary boundaries. Transgressive capabilities, the ones grounded in the desire for political impact, were found to be less common in these projects. While the NN+ researchers acknowledged that calls for investigating interconnections aren't particularly novel, they also admitted that the awareness of complexity did not previously translate into explicitly confronting it in their research. In the case of NN+ projects, researchers treated the WEF Nexus as a focal point around which complexity was embraced, rather than flattened entirely. They did so in two distinct ways; committing to radical interconnectedness, and reconceptualising (in)visibility.

Commitment to radical interconnectedness

One of the project researchers emphasised the importance of sustaining 'commitment to radical interconnectedness'ⁱⁱⁱ. This was perhaps the most characteristic feature of embracing nexus complexity in each stage of project. Through team and backstage capabilities which allow for radical interconnectedness, the WEF Nexus framing allowed de-centering each of the WEF domains and, aided in considering material, cultural and procedural dimensions of the interactions between water, energy, and food. It also cautioned researchers against inferring causality between water, energy, and food interactions. The WEF Nexus, as understood from a situated perspective, is not about creating ever-so-complex modelling tools which optimise (and, therefore, flatten) complex decisions. Instead, the goal was to design tools which help to reveal complexities and discuss them in teams involving researchers and practitioners.

Taking the notion of interconnections into account changes the process of sustainability appraisals: the researchers were forced to think about trade-offs and dilemmas and gained a critical distance from solutions they could have been previously inclined towards. At the same time, the applied orientation of the framework required researchers to come up with workable recommendations and diverse experts and lay publics, who are often excluded from sustainability research. For example, one of the research teams designed a toolkit for designing domestic sustainability interventions at the nexus of water, energy and food (Foden et al., 2019; Hoolohan et

al., 2018). The interactive worksheet was coproduced with policy partners, and it included challenges like the disposal of fats and greases blocking sewer systems or contemporary beauty standards which demand an increasing amount of water and energy. The toolkit allowed developing sustainable practices which consider several complexities (e.g. design of furniture or culture) rather than solely individual motivations. In this case, both the ambiguity and the normativity of the WEF Nexus buzzword were leveraged (Cairns and Krzywoszynska, 2016). The ambiguity allowed researchers to carve out novel conceptualisation while the normativity kept industry and policy partners on board.

In another case, the Co-Investigator of a NN+ project on agriculture remarked on the allure of seemingly simple solutions to complex problems: 'We thought we found a quick fix for growing food during drought – harvesting rainwater to grow more crops. But then, an epidemiologist came in and said, 'You're going to increase mosquitoes, and cause malaria from that'^{iv}. In ways like this, the WEF Nexus provoked NN+ researchers to develop reflexive and humble stances regarding the assumptions inherited from their own disciplines and theoretical approaches. NN+ projects demonstrated that instead of launching to announce quick and easy wins for sustainability, researchers and practitioners engaged with people in the peripheries of their expertise.

As shown on the example of the agriculture research project, the NN+ enabled novel configurations of expertise. If it wasn't for the hype around the WEF Nexus, researchers would have fewer incentives to build teams which include experts at the periphery of the main research questions. The excitement around the (seemingly) novel buzzword allowed for a degree of experimentation with regards to what constitutes a 'dream team' to solve a particular interdisciplinary sustainability challenge. For example, the PI of the agriculture project admitted during the interview that the NN+-funded project was conducted concurrently to a very similar, 'sister project', which shared 5 out of 10 project members in total'. In the following years, the same researchers successfully bid for a subsequent grant of over £920,000, effectively turning a research project into a decade-long research agenda.

Reconceptualising invisibility and calculability

In another illustrative example, a group of NN+ researchers trained in social practice theory noticed how their thinking evolved to conceptualise (in)visibility and materiality of resources. Remarking on the 'literal invisibility' of energy, they contrasted with tangible and sensuous food'^{vi}. They highlighted, however, that invisibility can also manifest in a metaphorical way, such as through routine and normalised consumption of services and products (e.g., heating). While social practice theory has traditionally proposed the notion of inconspicuous consumption, the NN+ researchers utilised nexus thinking to reconsider under what circumstances the consumption of environmental resources becomes visible. In doing so, they challenged the argument of inconspicuous consumption of energy. By finding connections across the WEF Nexus, they realised that 'escalating energy and water use can very well be explained by the fact that people want to have a big kitchen, or, you know, clean clothes every day and so on. Energy is not always invisible'^{vii}. Re-materialising energy consumption

by illustrating the links to tangible, status-oriented or aesthetic domestic practices (e.g., using a fireplace or garden pizza ovens) provides a fresh opportunity to engage the consumers with sustainable energy issues beyond the technical debates about infrastructures, renewables, and smart meters.

Our argument, however, goes beyond materiality. The differences in *calculability* across the WEF nexus also tend to skew policy response, highlighting the need for expert attention in some places and leaving funding gaps in others. Thinking about the ways human activities create greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, this calculation is readily available in the energy domain, while much more contestable when it comes to food (due to a huge variety in produce) and water (due to territorial dependencies) (Cusworth and Brice, 2022). This disparity is notable in climate policy. The UK Government accounting of territorial GHG emissions estimates that 26% percent of UK emissions come from transport, 20% from energy supply, and this is where the current focus of climate governance lies (BEIS, 2021). With barely 11% of the UK’s territorial GHG emissions originating from agriculture and so-called embedded^{viii} emissions from imported produce being absent from calculations, no wonder that when it comes to climate change, food continues to be framed as an issue of individual choice rather than one of agricultural policy and political action. So, if climate policy is skewed towards energy^{ix} from the outset – the researchers asked – ‘can we be even-handed with our treatment of water, energy and food?’^x.

So far, our research showed how the WEF Nexus allowed researchers to reconsider the complexity in interconnections, invisibility and calculability across water, energy and food domains. What’s worth noting, those complexities have already tilted the playing field in given directions. The conditions for nexus thinking are already stained with a rich patina of policies and politics of funders, incumbent research players and political actors. And so, as well as requiring cognitive capabilities to reconceptualise complexity, the WEF Nexus researchers will also need capabilities to acknowledge, and indeed challenge, power. Table 1 illustrates the aforementioned cognitive capabilities to address complexity in sustainability research.

Table 1. Capabilities to address complexity

How the WEF Nexus mobilised capabilities to deal with complexity:	Relevant cognitive capabilities:
Highlights the differences in materiality and calculability of different environmental resources	A cognitive capability to perform research across disciplinary boundaries A cognitive capability to apply tools and frameworks in new situations
Brings about a commitment to the equal treatment of different environmental resources	
Highlights ways to think about (in)visibility of food, energy, water as well as the related services or products people consume	

Brings about commitment to thinking about interconnectedness in each stage of research design	A cognitive capability for the sustained appreciation for the importance of detail, context and contingency
Avoids falling into the trap of linear causality thinking	
Forces to think about trade-offs and dilemmas	
Avoids recommending simplistic solutions	

4.2. Missing transgressive capabilities: making knowledge political

In the previous section, we've seen how the WEF Nexus was central to mobilising cognitive capabilities to address complexity. This aligns with a somewhat traditional view of interdisciplinarity--as a form of knowledge production required to address challenges that do not fall neatly along disciplinary lines (Barry, Born and Weszkalnys, 2008). Cognitive capabilities that support such interdisciplinary practices are necessary, and we have shown they were present within NN+ research projects. But crucially, they are not sufficient. After all, simply mobilising ever more expert knowledge is not by itself a remedy for sense-making of complex matters – indeed, if anything, it is a route to an endless spiral of complexity in itself (Sarewitz, 2004).

What is required--and explicitly demanded by researchers in our study--are capabilities to address power in knowledge production^{xi}. In other words, practices of knowledge production that effectively link scientific and technological advances with the needs of marginalised people (Stirling, 2015). To be clear, these are not necessarily capabilities to ferment widespread societal change, although sometimes these too are implicated in transdisciplinary research. But more often than not, they are the more mundane practices of negotiation, agreement, and collaboration. Practices such as establishing trust necessary to agree on meaningful research questions with community partners or battling university bureaucracy in establishing payment runs for overseas partners^{xii}. Crucial to these kinds of research practices are capabilities to appreciate plural knowledge, to establish collaborations, and to build collegiate and societal capacity for democratic struggle. These 'transgressive' capabilities as situated at both interpersonal and institutional levels, requiring commitments from researchers as well as programmes or funders.

How successful the buzzwords like 'the WEF Nexus' can be in convening capabilities where power might be acknowledged and addressed? Despite the promise of the NN+ engaging with the Water-Energy-Food Nexus from a social science standpoint, its ability to be critical was not a given. The WEF Nexus had convening power to productively gather people, funding, and concepts: 'The impression I got was the buzz aspect of it – of it being a buzzword... Sometimes you should be strategic and use the buzz to create something useful and interesting while you still can.'^{xiii} In one sense this convening power is instrumental. By the time it was mobilised by the ESRC Nexus Network+, the WEF Nexus represented a pot of research funding. Indeed, when we asked one researcher what was important to her about the term 'nexus', she laughed and replied: 'it gave us some money'^{xiv}.

In other words, the Nexus Network+ provided funding for research, but it was limited to the timeframes of the programme. Once the Network disbanded and the WEF Nexus term lost its popularity, it was difficult to continue research dissemination, political advocacy or even the upkeep of the professional networks built. In the words of Prof James Wilsdon (2017, p. 32), the co-director of the NN+, ‘there is a tension between the time, money and patience it takes to build meaningful interdisciplinary and cross-sector partnerships, and the attention span of funders. (...) Indeed, the March 2017 conference [organised by the NN+] represented a high-water mark in the development and deepening of the network, but this was also the point at which it was starting to wind down.’

This reveals how each of the NN+ projects attempted to leverage the WEF Nexus buzzword to make use of their existing transgressive capabilities. Importantly, the short time periods and limited funding of the NN+ programme, coupled with the conceptual ambiguity of the WEF Nexus buzzword, enabled researchers to capitalise on their existing agendas and capacities, but only if they were able to act quickly. This suggests that the value of buzzwords are not simply in the concepts themselves, but in the capacity of researchers to leverage *existing* capabilities through them. Looking next to backstage capabilities, we can further see the importance of pre-existing relationships, facilities, and resources.

4.3. Buzzwords and building backstage capabilities

The recognition of temporal nature of hype vis-a-vis the long-term requirements to translate sustainability research into transgressive, explicitly political practice is critical to understanding the lifecycle of the WEF Nexus and other buzzwords. On the one hand, buzzwords are the building blocks of knowledge infrastructures as they allow people to spur new collaborations (or continue the previous ones). On the other, buzzwords cease to maintain that infrastructure as soon as they lose popularity. As a consequence, researchers spend a lot of time building largely invisible backstage capabilities, their respective networks of people, facilities and resources, each of them requiring substantive repackaging to suit the next wave of hype.

Researchers’ backstage capabilities can be made visible once we shed light on how NN+ project used their funding. We already know that access to resources is rarely evenly distributed and often depends on where researchers are and the support in place (European Research Council, 2024). In practice, the NN+ funding of £60,000-120,000 could be a lot or a little, depending on the broader context. In one case, the project was effectively a continuation of a multi-decade programme led by a globally recognised PI, a project which allowed to pursue a novel research direction in otherwise well studied area. In another case, the NN+ project was conducted and promoted alongside an another, larger study, which allowed the PI to build a narrative of a string of successful grants in a short succession of time. In the third case, the NN+ project was a stand-alone early career researcher’s solo gig who didn’t work closely with the more established PI and Co-Is. Finally, one of the overseas projects were significantly hampered due to the lack of access to research infrastructure (e.g. journal articles or software licenses for data analysis) by the partners.

The Nexus Network+ was effectively a useful vehicle for mobilising backstage capabilities of established PI but less so, for budding early-career researchers or overseas partners. Rather than an opportunity, the WEF Nexus posed as a risk for scholars without the pre-existing backstage capabilities. As the framing emphasised combining domains and disciplines, it offered little commentary on what constitutes sufficient disciplinary grounding in the first place. This highlights wider issues, again, wherein the linguistic technology of buzzwords depends upon researchers' pre-existing absorptive capacity to flexibly adapt and adopt them to further their work. Like more traditional conceptualisations of technologies, buzzwords appear to enact both the knowledge embodied within as well as the meanings and knowledges of the actors using it.

Deploying buzzwords for research, therefore, requires a duty of care. First, funders ought to consider how networks are maintained once grants come to an end and to what extent the same networks can be upheld with the rise of a new buzzword. They should also re-consider the distribution of power in the international teams to avoid reproducing paternalistic funding structures. Finally, PIs ought to create postdoctoral roles which enable development of domain expertise rather than sole synthesis or translation.

4.4. Discussion

Capabilities for embracing complexity in sustainability all be observed as the researchers gathered around the WEF Nexus framing. Yet there remains somewhat of a tension here. The WEF Nexus offered the capabilities for researchers to use it strategically because they either had already or could rapidly cultivate backstage capabilities to establish networks and bridges between disciplinary boundaries. Perhaps then, we should understand the WEF Nexus buzzword not merely as an empty vessel waiting to be filled with meaning, but rather a bottle that already contains a message. WEF Nexus has already hinted at the possibility of integration but also allowed the possibility of *continuing previous* collaborations and a broadening out of research inputs. This was a factor in converting a buzzword into a real capability (Sen, 1999).

The capabilities discussed in the previous section are not merely a nice-to-have. They are essential if WEF Nexus framings are not to reinforce the existing power structures and usability of various types of knowledge. This is important because the ways in which WEF Nexus problems and possibilities are understood are profoundly value-laden and pervaded by sectoral interests. The danger is that if such interests are concealed within the ambiguity of buzzwords, interdisciplinary integration becomes and instrumentalised end-in-itself. That is, a technical task often defined narrowly in terms of economic efficiencies, rather than, for example, sustainably produced and equitably distributed water, energy, and food^{xv}.

So, what is required then? There is a clear need to address the hidden and invisible dimensions of power that WEF Nexus approaches and models neglect. This requires methodological diversity to facilitate pluralistic dialogue and synergies in knowledge

production. Social science and in particular fields tuned to epistemic power such as STS are well placed to contribute. But when the social and political dimensions of the WEF Nexus are unpacked, the dominant positivist framings of water, energy and food get more complex still. So beyond simply adding social science via interdisciplinary approaches, transdisciplinary capacity is required, that can extend beyond homogenising frames of knowledge production that have long colonised practices through target-oriented top-down framings (Mehta and Srivastava, 2020).

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we set to investigate how researchers engage with sustainability buzzwords, while avoiding the pitfalls of reactionary and shallow conceptualisations of complexity. We offer a close examination of how knowledge infrastructure comes into being within the situated practices of WEF Nexus research. Through the application of capability approach as our analytical lens, we were able to distinguish between capabilities already at hand and capabilities generated by the NN+ projects. Our analysis highlights three key points about engaging with the buzzwords like the WEF Nexus.

First, theoretical engagements with the WEF Nexus advanced its ability to conceptualise complexity in inter- and transdisciplinary sustainability research and praxis. We posit that the WEF Nexus could be a useful tool for social scientists who seek to understand materiality and calculability of environmental resources. Through theoretical engagements outside of their disciplines, and outside of their narrow sectors, the mobilisation of WEF Nexus as a buzzword leads researchers to more productive interactions across boundaries.

Second, we showed how the ambiguity of the WEF Nexus was used strategically by established researchers, who cultivated their pre-existing backstage capabilities to establish bridges between disciplinary boundaries. Through the WEF Nexus' practical ambiguity, the range of possible methods of engagement was increased, enabling pre-existing networks to be better leveraged than novel teams. It is this cultivation and maintenance of backstage capabilities which enables the leveraging of buzzword-related opportunities. However, this wasn't true for researchers in early career stages.

Third, we argue that inter- and transdisciplinary research is an inherently value-laden and political praxis. Buzzwords like the WEF Nexus can be utilised to engage with political questions of radical systemic change. However, these concerns can only be addressed if the researchers are able to cultivate their capabilities to challenge incumbency and existing power relations. Hence, buzzwords in sustainability should not be dismissed out of hand, but rather, used carefully to build knowledge infrastructures, i.e. professional networks, policy advice and external communication. Therefore, what is needed are knowledge practices and the production of underlying capabilities that instead of seeking to manage uncertainty in complexity, shift towards and practice 'doubt rather than uncertainty, scepticism rather than credulity and dissent rather than conformity', towards what Scoones and Stirling (2020, p. 11) call 'creative care rather than calculative control'.

In sum, we showed that the WEF Nexus buzzword facilitated researchers thinking better about complexity in sustainability. This yielded numerous success stories of unique team composition, bidding for related projects and gaining novel insights about the interactions across water, energy and food. However, the WEF Nexus' influence on policy could not be taken for granted. As the hype faded, researchers and programme leads were less able to translate their research agendas into transgressive, political action. This was particularly visible in the case of early career and overseas scholars who did not have the pre-existing networks of contacts or access to equipment, ready to re-assemble for the next fad. This paper's primary theoretical contribution was an articulation of the theory on fads and promises in science in relation to formal and informal knowledge infrastructures required to genuinely influence sustainability policy and politics. As interdisciplinary research on sustainability grows in popularity (Silvast and Foulds, 2022), this paper demonstrated the potential of buzzwords for infrastructuring, albeit under very constrained conditions. Going further, we hope the attention of STS scholars will turn to the issues of policy influence and researchers' precarity.

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ⁱ both authors were awarded with the NN+ funding to work on the referenced paper

ⁱⁱ this is a play on Anthony Giddens's notion of 'structuration' to evoke the mutually constructive character of agency and structure.

ⁱⁱⁱ Interview with a research associate, project 1; 20th Aug 2018

^{iv} Interview with a co-investigator, project 3; 22nd Aug 2018

^v Interview with the principal investigator, project 3; 23rd Aug 2018

^{vi} Interview with a co-investigator, project 1; 12th Sept 2018

^{vii} Interview with a co-investigator, project 1; 12th Sept 2018

^{viii} Embedded emissions are attributed to the whole lifecycle of a product rather than a country of origin. The UK imports 46% of food it consumes ([DEFRA, 2021](#))

^{ix ix} Discussions from workshop 2, May 2018

^x Interview with a research associate, project 1; 20th Aug 2018

^{xi} Discussions at a 'Maps, Measures and Narratives' workshop coordinated by the ESRC Nexus Network at the UCL Institute of Global Prosperity on 1 May 2018 drew on experiences of researchers funded by the NN+. They expressed perspectives on power in terms of which researchers have agency, who frames the problems, who selects the methods; how power imbalances persist and different levels of hierarchy exist across transdisciplinary partnerships; the power dynamics of knowledge brokering.

^{xii} Interview with co-investigator, project 4, 16th Aug 2018

^{xiii} Interview with a research associate, project 1; 20th Aug 2018

^{xiv} Interview with a co-investigator, project 1; 22nd Aug 2018

^{xv} These observations were informed by discussions one of the authors had with Rose Cairns, Saurabh Arora, Andy Stirling and James Wilsdon in their role as co-investigators of the Nexus Network +, 2014-2018.

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